

Synthesis and Biological Activity of some 2-Aryl-4*H*-1-benzopyran-4-ones

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A new three-step synthesis of 2-(4-aminophenyl)-4*H*-1-benzopyran-4-one (4) is reported. 2-[4-(2-Arylthiazolidin-4-one-3-yl)-phenyl]-4*H*-1-benzopyran-4-one (6a-c) and 2-[4-(4-arylazetidino-2-one-1-yl)phenyl]-4*H*-1-benzopyran-4-one (7a-c) have been synthesised from the *N*-arylidene derivatives (5a-d) of 2-(4-aminophenyl)-4*H*-1-benzopyran-4-one. Formation of 2-(4-acetoacetamidophenyl)-4*H*-1-benzopyran-4-one (8) and 2-(4-benzoylmethylamidophenyl)-4*H*-1-benzopyran-4-one (9) are also reported. *N*-Acyl derivatives (10a-c) have been prepared and 2-[4-(2-chloroacetamido)phenyl]-4*H*-1-benzopyran-4-one (10a) has been reacted with secondary amines and other nucleophiles to yield 11a-d, 12 and 13. Preliminary studies have shown biological activity for some of the compounds.

4*H*-1-Benzopyran-4-ones are known to possess a wide range of biological activities¹. In view of this, we have continued our studies^{2,3} on the synthesis and biological evaluation of 2-(4-aryl)-4*H*-1-benzopyran-4-ones.

2-(4-Aminophenyl)-4*H*-1-benzopyran-4-one (4) was synthesised by the acid hydrolysis of 2-(4-acetamidophenyl)-4*H*-1-benzopyran-4-one (3). This route gave better yields than the methods earlier reported³ involving reduction of 2-(4-nitrophenyl)-4*H*-1-benzopyran-4-one.

4-Acetamidobenzoic acid was condensed with 2-hydroxyacetophenone using POCl₃-pyridine to yield 2-(4-acetamidobenzoyloxy)acetophenone (1) which was subjected to Baker-Venkataraman rearrangement to give (2-hydroxybenzoyl)(4-acetamidobenzoyl)methane (2). Acid-catalysed cyclodehydration of 2 in EtOH-H₂SO₄ yielded 3 which was hydrolysed to 4 in EtOH-HCl; alternatively, cyclodehydration of 2 in EtOH-HCl yielded 4 directly (Scheme 1). The structure of 4 obtained by this route was confirmed by comparison with an authentic sample.

Scheme 1

Compound 4 was condensed with aromatic aldehydes to give *N*-arylidene derivatives (5a-d) (Scheme 2) which on treatment with thioglycolic acid in benzene yielded the expected 2-[4-(2-arylthiazolidin-4-one-3-yl)phenyl]-4*H*-1-benzopyran-4-ones

(6a-c). Treatment of 5a-c with chloroacetyl chloride and triethylamine in benzene afforded the 2-[4-(4-aryl-3-chloroazetidino-2-one-1-yl)phenyl]-4*H*-1-benzopyran-4-ones (7a-c).

Scheme 2

The reaction of 4 with ethyl acetoacetate yielded 2-(4-acetoacetamidophenyl)-4*H*-1-benzopyran-4-one (8). Reaction with ω -bromoacetophenone yielded 2-(4-benzoylmethylamidophenyl)-4*H*-1-benzopyran-4-one (9). Compound 4 on treatment with acid chlorides in the presence of a mild base (such as potassium carbonate, pyridine, triethylamine, etc.) yielded the *N*-acyl derivatives (10a-c).

2-[4-(2-Chloroacetamido)phenyl]-4*H*-1-benzopyran-4-one (10a) was reacted with secondary amines, hydrazine hydrate, KNCS and KCN to give 11a-d, 12 and 13 respectively. Ir spectral data confirm that the 4*H*-1-benzopyran-4-one system remained intact (Scheme 3).

Compounds 1-13 were evaluated for their *in vitro*

(0.002 mol) in dry benzene (20 ml), chloroacetyl chloride (0.002 mol) in dry benzene (5 ml) was added. The mixture was then refluxed 30 min, cooled, filtered and the filtrate evaporated. The residue thus obtained was crystallised from methanol : **7a**, (35%), m.p. 168°, ν_{\max} 2 966, 1 775 (azetidinone C=O), 1 650 (benzopyrone C=O), 1 615, 1 575, 1 380 and 765 cm^{-1} (C—Cl); δ (CDCl_3) 4.65 (1H, d, *J* 2 Hz, azetidinone H-4), 5.05 (1H, d, *J* 2 Hz, azetidinone H-3), 6.7 (1H, s, benzopyrone H-3) and 7.2–8.2 (12H, m, ArH); **b** (64%), 135°, ν_{\max} 2 955, 1 775 (azetidinone C=O), 1 640 (benzopyrone C=O), 1 615, 1 560, 1 385 and 760 cm^{-1} (C—Cl); δ (CDCl_3) 2.3 (3H, s, Ar—CH₃) 4.45 (1H, d, *J* 2 Hz, azetidinone H-4), 5.15 (1H, d, *J* 2 Hz, azetidinone H-3), 6.7 (1H, s, benzopyrone H-3) and 7.2–8.2 (12H, m, ArH); **c** (48%), 183°, ν_{\max} 2 950, 1 770 (azetidinone C=O), 1 640 (benzopyrone C=O), 1 615, 1 565, 1 380 and 765 cm^{-1} (C—Cl); δ (CDCl_3) 4.5 (1H, d, *J* 2 Hz, azetidinone H-4), 5.0 (1H, d, *J* 2 Hz, azetidinone H-3), 6.7 (1H, s, benzopyrone H-3) and 7.1–8.2 (13H, m, ArH).

2-(4-Acetoacetamidophenyl)-4H-1-benzopyran-4-one (8): Compound **4** (0.001 mol) was heated in ethyl acetoacetate (2 ml) at 150° for 3 h. The solid which separated on cooling was fractionally crystallised from chloroform-ethanol, (29%), m.p. 211°; ν_{\max} 3 300–3 050 (NH), 1 725 (C=O), 1 700 (amide) and 1 640 cm^{-1} (benzopyrone C=O); δ (CDCl_3) 2.2 (3H, s, CH₃), 3.5 (2H, s, CH₂), 6.7 (1H, s, benzopyrone H-3), 7.6–8.2 (8H, m, ArH) and 10.15 (1H, s, exchangeable, NH—CO).

2-(4-Benzoylmethylaminophenyl)-4H-1-benzopyran-4-one (9): A mixture of compound **4** (0.002 mol) and ω -bromoacetophenone (0.0025 mol) was refluxed 10 h in dry acetone (20 ml) containing anhydrous potassium carbonate (1 g). The solvent was then evaporated, the residue washed with dilute HCl (10%) followed by water and the resulting solid was crystallised from chloroform-ethanol, (32%), m.p. 243°; ν_{\max} 3 400 (NH), 1 690 (benzoyl C=O) and 1 640 (benzopyrone C=O); δ ($\text{CDCl}_3 + \text{DMSO-d}_6$) 3.5 (2H, s, CH₂), 4.2 (1H, br s, NH), 6.8 (1H, s, benzopyrone H-3) and 7.0–8.2 (13H, m, ArH).

2-(4-Acylamidophenyl)-4-H1-benzopyran-4-ones (10a–c). *General procedure*: To a suspension of **4** (0.005 mol) and anhydrous potassium carbonate

(2.5 g)/pyridine/triethylamine (1 ml) in dry chloroform (75 ml) was added the appropriate acid chloride (e.g. chloroacetyl chloride, benzoyl chloride or acetyl chloride) (0.006 mol) and the mixture was refluxed for 3 h. The solvent was then evaporated, the resulting solid washed with cold water and crystallised from chloroform-ethanol : **10a**, (94%), m.p. 270°, ν_{\max} 3 250–2 900 (NH), 1 710 (amide), 1 640 (benzopyrone C=O), 1 610 and 720 cm^{-1} (C—Cl); δ (DMSO-d_6) 4.4 (2H, s, CH₂), 7.0 (1H, s, benzopyrone H-3), 7.75–8.3 (8H, m, ArH) and 10.7 (1H, br s, NH—CO); **b** (84%), 255°, ν_{\max} 3 350–3 075 (NH), 1 715 (amide C=O), 1 640 (benzopyrone C=O), 1 600, 1 545, 1 520 and 1 255 cm^{-1} ; δ (DMSO-d_6) 6.8 (1H, s, benzopyrone H-3), 7.0–8.4 (13H, m, ArH) and 10.2 (1H, s, NH—CO); **c** (87%), m.p. 238°, ν_{\max} 3 260–3 100 (NH), 1 700 (amide C=O) and 1 640 cm^{-1} (benzopyrone C=O); δ (CDCl_3) 2.15 (3H, s, CH₃), 6.65 (1H, s, benzopyrone H-3), 7.35–8.2 (8H, m, ArH) and 9.35 (1H, s, NH—CO).

Substitution reactions of 10a. General procedure

A mixture of compound **10a** (0.001 mol) and the appropriate reagent (e.g. piperidine, morpholine, diethanolamine, hydrazine hydrate, KNCS or KCN) (0.015 mol) was refluxed in dry ethanol (20 ml) for 6 h. It was then filtered hot and concentrated to half of its volume. The resulting solid was recrystallised from ethanol: **11a** (75%), m.p. 181°; **11b** (65), 205°; **11c** (78), 214°; **11d** (57), 255°; **12** (60), 260°; **13** (45), 202°.

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